

METHODOLOGICAL GUIDELINES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' SKILLS IN DATA ANALYSIS IN PHYSICS IN PROBLEM-BASED LEARNING THROUGH DIALOGUE**Bimagambetova A.***Master, 1 st course, Yessenov University***Bizhanova K.***Scientific Supervisor**Candidate of Physical and Mathematical Sciences, Professor***Abstract**

This article presents innovative methodological guidelines for advancing students' data analysis skills in physics through problem-based learning with a focus on dialogue. It explores the use of dialogic methods and structured tasks to cultivate students' critical thinking and analytical abilities, setting this approach apart from traditional teaching methods. By incorporating dialogue, the guidelines aim to engage students in deeper analysis, allowing them to formulate hypotheses, interpret complex data, and apply insights to real-world contexts. Additionally, the article provides teachers with practical strategies to encourage student interaction and reflection, promoting data competency as a core skill. These recommendations underscore the value of dialogue in the learning process, establishing it as an effective tool to improve educational outcomes in physics and related disciplines. The significance of this work lies in its potential to transform teaching practices and equip students with essential skills for both academic and practical problem-solving.

Keywords: problem-based learning, dialogue, data analysis, critical thinking, methodological recommendations, analytical skills, education, teaching methods.

Introduction

Modern educational methods increasingly emphasize the need to develop students' critical thinking and analytical abilities. Data analysis skills play a crucial role in solving complex problems in physics. Research shows that problem-based learning through dialogue is an effective approach for students to develop these skills, as it encourages them to exchange ideas and analyze information [1].

Theoretical Basis: At the heart of the problem-based learning method is the enhancement of students' critical thinking skills. This method encourages students to analyze real-life problems and make decisions, enabling them to learn to solve issues using their knowledge [3]. For example, when studying the motion of objects according to Newton's second law in a physics lesson, students may be asked to determine how the forces of friction and gravity affect that motion. Such tasks are grounded in real-life problems, which activate

students' cognitive engagement and develop their analytical abilities [2].

Methodological recommendations: For the development of data analysis skills, for the effective use of dialogue, teachers need to properly organize the educational process [5]. The recommendations presented below will help with this.

1. Organization of Dialogue Sessions: Each class aimed at developing analytical skills should include dialogue sessions where students can discuss the proposed tasks. It is advisable to divide students into small groups of 3 to 5 members, ensuring that everyone has the opportunity to express their opinions and listen to others. For example, on the topic of "thermal energy," students are divided into groups to discuss the distribution of energy during the process of heating water. They analyze data presented in tables, identify key trends, and determine the factors affecting the boiling point of water.

Figure-1

2. Problem situations as an incentive for dialogue. When the dialogue is most effective, students face real problems that need to be analyzed. The teacher can give students a task on the topic of Ecology, which can be considered an example of analyzing the effect of

rising CO₂ levels on atmospheric temperature. By providing a graph showing changes in the amount of CO₂ over the past 50 years, students discuss various factors within the group, such as the development of industrial cities and deforestation.

CO₂ Concentration and Atmospheric Temperature Over Time

Figure-2

3. Tasks for Data Analysis: To apply theoretical knowledge in practical work, it is essential to provide students with tasks that allow them to use their knowledge in practice. Such tasks include analyzing statistical data, making comparisons, and drawing conclusions based on this data. For example, in the topic of kinematics in physics, students are asked to analyze the trajectories of objects moving at different speeds. They illustrate the relationship between speed and time on a graph and calculate the average speed for each case. This enables students to analyze data presented in both tables and graphs [3].

4. Using Graphical Tools: When teaching data analysis, it is crucial to utilize visual aids such as graphs, charts, and tables. These tools help students better understand the structure of the data and quickly identify key trends. In preparing dialogue sessions, the teacher can use graphical representations of the data that students must interpret and discuss.

For example, by presenting a graph of the relationship between current and voltage on the topic of Ohm's Law, students gain a clearer understanding of the basic concepts in electrical engineering.

Figure-3

Practical Tasks: To effectively apply theoretical knowledge during lessons, it is essential to provide students with specific tasks that stimulate analytical thinking. Within the framework of problem-based learning in physics, tasks aimed at studying specific physical phenomena can be employed to develop data analysis skills. For example, to analyze the relationship between pressure and temperature, students are given data on pressure and temperature in regions located at different altitudes. They seek answers to questions based on this data and attempt to identify underlying physical laws.

Case Model: Students are presented with data on changes in atmospheric pressure and temperature in different regions over the past 10 years. Their task is to discuss the following questions based on this data:

- How has pressure changed at different altitudes?
- In which areas were the highest and lowest pressure levels observed?
- How do natural phenomena or climatic factors influence these changes?
- How can physical laws, such as Boyle's and Gay-Lussac's laws, be interpreted based on the data?

This task helps students understand the relationship between physical laws and natural phenomena. After analyzing the data, students build graphs to illustrate the relationship between pressure and temperature. Following their group discussions, they present their results to the class and support their conclusions with evidence.

Evaluation of Results: The assessment of students' work takes into account their understanding of physical data and their analysis of specific physical phenomena. The teacher can use the following criteria:

1. **Active Participation in Discussion and Presentation of Evidence:** This criterion evaluates students' ability to actively engage in the task and present evidence that aligns with physical laws.

2. **Ability to Analyze Data:** This criterion assesses students' logical and accurate analysis of the presented physical data.

3. **Use of Graphical Data:** This criterion measures students' ability to visually explain physical phenomena using graphs and diagrams.

Additional Advice for Teachers:

- **Structuring the Dialogue:** The teacher should guide the discussion by asking questions that enable students to engage in a dialogue based on physical data.
- **Encouraging Critical Thinking:** Pose questions that encourage students to think more deeply and broaden their perspectives.
- **Utilizing Diverse Data:** Foster students' ability to apply their knowledge in practice by providing them with various data sets to analyze different physical phenomena.

Conclusion:

The use of dialogue within problem-based learning is a powerful tool for developing students' data analysis skills. Engaging in discussions about specific problems based on data not only enhances students' analytical abilities but also teaches them to think critically, collaborate effectively, and substantiate their viewpoints. The proposed methodological guidelines will assist teachers in effectively implementing these strategies in practice.

Dialogue plays a crucial role in collaborative projects within problem-based learning. Students who actively participate in dialogue gain a deeper understanding of the problems and develop higher-quality solutions. This improvement arises from the fact that dialogue fosters the collaborative creation of knowledge and the exchange of ideas among students, particularly in complex tasks that demand critical thinking [4].

References

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